

KonsortSWD Measure 5.1: Metadata schema extension for new entity types

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Abstract

The persistent identifiers (PIDs) assigned to the level of fragments, i.e., a variable in Social Science research data, can unambiguously cite and directly retrieve data. Variables evolve over time, linking survey waves, studies, questions, and concepts. Given the importance of variables and their ties, the associated metadata must capture these relations and allow machine-actionable features through PIDs and controlled vocabulary (CV) terms. The KonsortSWD "Measure TA.5-M.1 Enhancing PID services as a base for a FAIR data infrastructure" outputs a PID registration, and the basic metadata schema needs to be extended to meet the new dataset types, such as questions and answers, audio, and video segments.

Keywords:

Persistent Identifiers - PIDs. Research data citation. Research data - Social Sciences. Variables - Social Sciences. Granular data citation. Research data infrastructure. Metadata schema.

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1. Introduction

The KonsortSWD “Measure TA.5-M.1 Enhancing PID services as a base for a FAIR data infrastructure” [1] first targeted variables as the smallest PID-assigned units in social science datasets. Milestone 5 extends this approach to new entity types, including questions and answers, audio/video segments, text excerpts, transcripts, and image areas. The extended metadata schema [2] provided the minimal metadata to assign a PID to the entities (variables) within a dataset. These new entities require minimal metadata for PID registration while preserving interoperability, supporting controlled vocabularies (CVs), and enabling machine-actionable features at the fragment level.

Table 1 provides an overview of the first PID registration schema, addressing the properties of variables and semantics. To provide a more generic metadata schema [3], we proposed the “entity name” and “entity label” as metadata fields to register the type of ID (entity name) and the description of the variable as “label.” Column 3 in Table 1 indicates whether the property is required and must-have information for the metadata validation within the PID registration service. The DataCite level of obligation is also shown in column 4, such as Mandatory (M), the property is obligatory; Recommended (R), the property is valuable and should be added; and Optional (O), the property may be added.

ID	FIELD NAME	DESCRIPTION	PID SERVICE LEVEL OF REQUIREMENT	DATA CITE LEVEL OF OBLIGATION	KNOWLEDGE GRAPH POTENTIAL METADATA FIELDS / SUBFIELDS
1	Study DOI*	A DOI or any PID: The DOI identifies the study or the Dataset where the variable to register appears.	Required for any PID Required for DOI Standard	Mandatory (M) (with mandatory type sub-property) Identifier_Type	Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for objects and research outputs ¹
2	Entity Name	The name of the variable to register In this case, a variable.	Required for any PID	Not a DataCite core field	
3	Entity Label	The label of the variable to register, In this case, a variable.	Required for any PID	Not a DataCite core field	
4	PID Proposal*	The PID proposal for the variable to register. The user must provide the PID proposal. Each institution registering variables can have a specific prefix and provide a proposal for registering the variable.	Required for any PID	N/A (process requirement, not schema)	PID syntax <doi_Proposal>Your prefix/Your suffix</doi_Proposal>
5	Landing Page*	The (URL) landing page of the variable to register, via which a user may obtain detailed information about the variable to register.	Required for any PID Required for the DOI standard	Mandatory (M)	URL Address
6	Resource type*	The type of the resource	Required for any PID Required for DOI standard registration	Mandatory (M) (with mandatory general type description sub-property)	Controlled List Values
7	Title	The title of the resource to register, which is generated by the registration service using the entity name and the entity label combination	Required for any PID Required for the DOI standard	Mandatory (M) (with optional type sub-properties)	
8	Creators	The creators of the variable to register. Leading researchers are involved. Note that the creators may be different from those of the study. Multiple entries are possible. It may be a corporate/institutional or personal name.	Required for any PID Required for the DOI standard	Mandatory (M)	

¹ Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), Archival Resource Key identifiers (ARKs), the Handle system (governed by the independent Swiss DONA Foundation and used by DOI, ePIC and many other service providers), International Generic Sample Number (IGSNs), Uniform Resource Name (URN), Persistent Uniform Resource Locators (PURL), Research Activity Identifier (RAiD), Research resource identifiers (RRID), Uniform Resource Identifier (URI), and Universally Unique Identifiers (UUID).

ID	FIELD NAME	DESCRIPTION	PID SERVICE LEVEL OF REQUIREMENT	DATA CITE LEVEL OF OBLIGATION	KNOWLEDGE GRAPH POTENTIAL METADATA FIELDS / SUBFIELDS
9	Publisher	The name of the entity that holds, archives, publishes prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces the Resource	Required for any PID Required for the DOI standard	Mandatory (M)	
10	Publication date YYYY-MM-DD	The date of the publication of the study in which the variable to register appears	Required for any PID Required for the DOI standard	Mandatory (M) (year) / Recommended (full date)	
11	Availability	The conditions governing access to the resource are download, access under contract, open access, login required, etc.	Required for any PID Required for the DOI standard	Optional (O) Metadata field is 'Rights' and instructed as 'free text1'	Controlled List Values
12	Description/ Abstract	All additional information that does not fit in any of the other categories	Optional (O)	Recommended (R)	

Table 1: Generic metadata labels are used to register a variable PID.

Further documentation, such as the question and answers/responses schema, or descriptive fields within DDI (Data Documentation Initiative, 2020), is unnecessary to obtain a PID. However, the metadata schema is now extended to meet the increasing demand for interoperability, data mappings, and particularities of registered entities.

Section 2 explains the interconnected nature of research entities, particularly variables and the elements linked to them within social science research metadata.

2. New entities and relationships

Variables remain a core entity in social science research, serving as the primary framework for organizing and interpreting data. However, they are inherently linked to other critical elements. Questions and answers, representing the response domain, are often connected to variables in one-to-one, one-to-many, or many-to-one relationships. Qualitative segments (text excerpts, audio/video segments, image areas) are always linked to a broader parent resource, such as a full transcript or video. This section states that *Relation_Type* terms from the DataCite controlled vocabulary are used to describe these links. This ensures that navigation between related entities is explicit and machine-actionable.

To describe these relationships, the DataCite metadata schema's controlled vocabulary for *Relation_Type* is employed. Terms like *IsPartOf* are particularly useful, as they explicitly capture

the hierarchical link between an entity and its parent. For example, *IsPartOf* can describe the relationship between a variable and the dataset from which it originates (See Table 2).

Registering persistent identifiers (PIDs) for variables alone is not sufficient. Registering questions and answers with their own PIDs supports interoperability and enables accurate linkage across systems. This requires defining a minimum set of metadata fields that can be stored in a *RelatedItem* container, together with the appropriate controlled vocabulary terms for *Relation_Type*. Such terms ensure that the nature of each relationship is clearly understood and consistently applied.

Extending the PID registration service to incorporate these relationship fields will allow for the registration of additional entity types beyond variables, including qualitative data that are non-numeric and non-coded. This enhancement supports FAIR principles by enabling richer interlinking of research entities, improving findability, and facilitating reproducibility.

Relation Type	Definition	Usage Notes
IsPartOf	Indicates A is a portion of B; may be used for elements of a series.	Primarily applied to container–contained type relationships. Note: May be used for individual software modules; code repository-to-version relationships should instead use IsVersionOf and HasVersion . Recommended for discovery. Example (XML): <relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="DOI" relationType="IsPartOf">10.5281/zenodo.754312</relatedIdentifier>

Table 2: IsPartOf: Relation_Type from DataCite metadata schema²

Table 3 shows the relations metadata fields extended in the PID Service metadata schema to represent relationships, and are helpful for knowledge graph outputs. These are the fields in which the values are standardized information, such as PIDs or controlled vocabularies, and can be machine-actionable to generate a visualization in a knowledge map format.

² <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/appendices/appendix-1/relationType/#ispartof>

ID	FIELD NAME	DESCRIPTION	PID SERVICE LEVEL OF REQUIREMENT	DATACITE LEVEL OF OBLIGATION	KNOWLEDGE GRAPH EXTENDED METADATA FIELDS / SUBFIELDS
13	RelatedItem	The related resource (B)	Optional (O)	Recommended (R)	Controlled List Values: resourceType ³ : Variable
13.1	RelatedIdentifier (12)	PIDs - The format is dependent upon the scheme	Optional (O)	Recommended (R) (with RelatedIdentifier_Type and Relation_Type)	PID ⁴
13.1.1	RelatedIdentifier_ Type (12. a)	Any PID system depends on the Scheme.	Optional (O)	Recommended (R)	PID system name ⁵
13.1.2	Relation_Type (12. b)	Description of the relationship between the registered resource (A) and the target- related resource (B)	Optional (O)	If RelatedIdentifier is used, relationType is mandatory (M).	Controlled List Values ⁶ : • IsContinuedBy • Continues • Describes • HasVersion • IsVersionOf • IsNewVersionOf • IsPreviousVersionOf • IsDocumentedBy • IsCompiledBy • IsVariantFormOf • IsDerivedFrom • IsSourceOf • IsRequiredBy • IsObsoletedBy

Table 3: Proposed [extended](#) metadata fields for registering a variable.

Considering our current need to update the PID registration service to extend the metadata schema, we suggest fields that suit the following entities, as well as non-numeric and non-coded data (qualitative data).

Section 3 addresses the challenge of defining controlled vocabulary (CV) terms for the [Resource_Type](#) field in a way that supports the precise registration of entities in the PID system. The TA5-M1 team has developed a minimal metadata schema designed to be both generic and interoperable, suitable for use with the Handle system.

³ <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/appendices/appendix-1/resourceTypeGeneral/#resourcetypegeneral>

⁴ <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/properties/relatedidentifier/>

⁵ <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/properties/relatedidentifier-relatedidentifiertype>

⁶ [Relation_Type](#) <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.6/appendices/appendix-1/relationType/#relationtype>

3. Alternatives for Controlled Vocabulary terms to describe *Resource_Type*

This section discusses alternatives for Controlled Vocabulary (CV) terms for the *Resource_Type* field in the context of the PID registration service. The TA5-M1 team focused on a minimal metadata schema necessary only to register the entity. It starts with variable type, while keeping the schema brief and generic, suitable for more than one PID system, e.g., the DOI and Handle systems.

The system should be ideal for getting PIDs from DataCite or ePIC APIs. Furthermore, it envisions the registration of other entity types beyond variables (e.g., survey questions, sound/video fragments, text files, transcript excerpts, and image areas). The required metadata, including the following properties, is already designed in the PID registration service [4] (See Table 1 and Table 2).

It reviews the CV terms from DataCite, FAIR Signposting/COAR Repositories, and daJra, assessing whether they are suitable for describing resources at this more granular level. The conclusion is that existing CVs operate primarily at high aggregation levels and lack the fragment-level specificity needed for Milestone 5. Therefore, a new set of CV terms is proposed to enable precise identification and citation of specific research entities.

3.1 Controlled vocabulary for *Resource_Type*

According to the PID registration service, the basic metadata schema [5] sets the metadata fields as mandatory or optional, depending on the PID system. There are fields required for assigning any PID and fields needed solely for the DOI standard. *Resource_Type* is a field required for any PID, and its description must be a controlled vocabulary aligned with community standards. These standards are listed below to demonstrate their suitability (or not) in providing such terms to address fragment or lower granularity dataset elements.

3.1.1 DataCite

Resource_type is a mandatory field. However, DataCite's Controlled Vocabulary does not provide a lower-level or finer-grained element term within its CV for *Resource_type* ⁷.

⁷ See <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.5/properties/resourcetype/>
<https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.5/appendices/appendix-1/resourceTypeGeneral/>

3.1.2 FAIR Signposting - Coar-Repositories

Coar-repositories Controlled Vocabulary, adopted by the FAIR Signposting standard, provides only study-level alternatives as Controlled Vocabulary terms addressing resource types. The most relevant term for our project is "survey data."⁸ Coar-repositories rely on terms from DDI and Dublin Core Metadata Terms (DCMI) for qualitative resource types. A complete list of Resource Type vocabulary from Coar-repositories is listed in Table 4 .

3.1.3 Da|Ra

ResourceType definition at da|ra [6] p.51 is the same as DataCite The available terms of our interest are

- Text
- Image
- Audiovisual
- Sound

4 Appendices

4.1 Appendix 1: da|ra Controlled Vocabulary Definitions

4.1.1 resourceType

da ra 3.1	da ra 4.0	
id	resourceType	definition ⁸
1	Collection	An aggregation of resources, which may encompass collections of one resourceType as well as those of mixed types. A collection is described as a group; its parts may also be separately described.
2	Dataset	Data encoded in a defined structure.
3	Text	A resource consisting primarily of words for reading.
4	deprecated; use Audiovisual instead	
	Software	A computer program in source code (text) or compiled form.
5	Image	A visual representation other than text.
6	deprecated; use Audiovisual instead	
	Audiovisual	A series of visual representations imparting an impression of motion when shown in succession. May or may not include sound.
	InteractiveResource	A resource requiring interaction from the user to be understood, executed, or experienced.
	DataPaper	A factual and objective publication with a focused intent to identify and describe specific data, sets of data, or data collections to facilitate discoverability.
	Event	A non-persistent, time-based occurrence.
	Model	An abstract, conceptual, graphical, mathematical or visualization model that represents empirical objects, phenomena, or physical processes.
	PhysicalObject	An inanimate, three-dimensional object or substance.
	Service	A system that provides one or more functions of value to the end-user.
	Sound	A resource primarily intended to be heard.
	Workflow	A structured series of steps which can be executed to produce a final outcome, allowing users a means to specify and enact their work in a more reproducible manner.
	Other	If selected, supply a value for resourceTypeFree.

Figure 1: da|ra Resource Type vocabulary

⁸ See https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/resource_types/ and https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/resource_types/NHD0-W6SY/

DataCite ⁹	Coar-repositories ¹⁰		Da Ra (adopts DataCite) ¹¹
Quantitative and Qualitative Data	Quantitative Data	Qualitative Data	Qualitative Data
Audiovisual	dataset	image	Text
Book	aggregated data	moving image	Image
BookChapter	clinical trial data	video	Audiovisual
Collection	compiled data	still image	Sound
ComputationalNotebook	encoded data	interactive resource	
ConferencePaper	experimental data	website	
ConferenceProceeding	genomic data	sound	
DataPaper	geospatial data	musical composition	
Dataset	laboratory notebook	text	
Dissertation	measurement and test data	annotation	
Event	observational data	bibliography	
Image	recorded data	blog post	
Instrument	simulation data	lecture	
InteractiveResource	survey data	...	
Journal			
JournalArticle			
Model			
OutputManagementPlan			
PeerReview			
PhysicalObject			
Preprint			
Report			
Service			
Software			
Sound			
Standard			
StudyRegistration			
Text			
Workflow			
Other			

Table 4: Comparison of Resource Type Vocabularies: DataCite, COAR Repositories, and Da|Ra.

⁹ <https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.5/appendices/appendix-1/resourceTypeGeneral/#resourcetypegeneral>

¹⁰ https://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/resource_types/

¹¹ <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:0168-ssoar-54937-1>

Since no established terms for variables or questions exist in current standards, this report takes its orientation from existing best practices on granularity from da|ra Best Practice: Granularity orientation. The da|ra model offers a clear framework for deciding how detailed metadata registration should be, particularly when differentiating between whole datasets and their elements.

3.1.3.1 da|ra Best Practice: Granularity

The da|ra approach illustrates how granularity choices affect publication and citation, setting the stage for extending controlled vocabularies. However, while this model clarifies levels of description, it does not yet provide specific terms for dataset elements such as variables, questions, or media segments. Addressing this gap requires a complementary controlled vocabulary.

When deciding which level of granularity is used to register a resource, two aspects are crucial: 1. which unit is to be published, and 2. at which level a citation is desired. As an illustration, some examples of granularity are depicted in Figure 2 [7].

Examples for granularity		
Resource type	Possible levels of granularity	Examples (fiktiv)
Dataset	A study	Panel study "Test"
	A particular survey year/wave of this study	Survey year 2005 of the panel study "Test"
	A specific sample (subsample) within a survey year/wave of a study	Cohort 4 in survey year 2005 of the panel study "Test"
	Data type (SUF, PUF, online etc.), file format (EXCEL, SPSS, STATA, R) or the language version of a data file	The STATA-file (.dta) of cohort 4 in survey year 2005 of the panel study "Test"
Text	A journal	The journal "Testing"
	A specific issue of this magazine (e. g. language version)	The journal "Testing" in German
	An article within this journal	The article "The panel study „Test“" in the German version of the journal "Testing"
Video	A video (of an interview, participant observation etc.)	Video of interviews for panel study "Test" in survey year 2005
	A video sequence in the video	Video of interviews from cohort 4

Figure 2: da|ra Best Practice: Granularity, version 1.0

Based on this principle of granularity, there is a clear need for more precise terminology to identify elements within datasets. The following section proposes a controlled vocabulary tailored to support PID registration and citation at the fragment level for quantitative and qualitative data. Milestone 5 addresses this gap in current standards by introducing terms enabling datasets and their more granular elements to persistently identify, cite, and link.

3.2 Controlled vocabulary for Resource_Type: selected terms

The selected vocabulary terms extend existing practices by introducing categories of quantitative and qualitative dataset elements. This enables repositories and PID infrastructures to treat variables, questions, and media segments as first-class, citable entities. The following section builds on this foundation by examining how established metadata standards can support the description of these entities at the required level of granularity.

To support Milestone 5, we propose adding terms such as *Variable*, *Question*, *Sound segment*, *Audiovisual segment*, *Text excerpt*, and *Image area*. Current vocabularies (e.g., DataCite, COAR, da|ra) describe resources at a broad level (like “dataset” or “image”) but do not capture their elements. This finer granularity is essential for assigning PIDs and enabling FAIR-compliant citation and discovery of specific research elements within both quantitative and qualitative data:

- Variable
- Question (response domain)
- Sound segment
- Audiovisual segment
- Text excerpt
- Image area

The proposed controlled vocabulary terms were defined to address a specific metadata gap at the level of granularity required by Milestone 5. No existing controlled vocabulary from DataCite, CoAR Repositories, da|ra, or other standards covers this finer granularity for identifying quantitative and qualitative dataset elements. Current vocabularies tend to operate at a higher aggregation level (e.g., “dataset,” “survey data,” “image,” “sound”) without distinguishing between a whole resource and its elements. This lack of precision for PID registration and FAIR-compliant interlinking prevents accurate identification and citation of specific research entities.

The selection of these terms follows best practice recommendations in that it ensures the ResourceType field is populated with precise, machine-actionable, and consistently applied terminology. Wherever possible, the terms draw on concepts already in use in the social sciences and digital preservation communities (e.g., DDI Alliance model), while introducing the explicit fragment-level categories needed for reproducible citation. They support

interoperability and machine-actionable metadata by enabling PID systems to differentiate between entire resources and elements. It is essential for knowledge graph construction and linking related entities, such as a variable and the question that produced it, or a transcript excerpt and its parent interview.

Curators and repositories must be able to register and cite these elements individually, not only at the dataset level, to facilitate precise referencing, reproducibility, and interoperability. By adopting these controlled vocabulary terms, the PID registration service can classify and relate diverse data objects at the fragment level.

Section 4 Examines alternatives for describing the entities documented in the *Resource_Type* field, focusing on the finer granularity needed to register specific segments and elements. To achieve this, various metadata standards and repositories were analyzed to identify common practices and field definitions.

4. Metadata fields for specific segments

This section of the document presents possible alternatives for describing metadata fields for the entities recorded in the *Resource_Type* field, especially at a more granular level (e.g., variables, questions, audiovisual segments, text excerpts, and image areas). It compares standards, practices, and field structures from various metadata providers (GESIS¹², DDI Alliance¹³, CESSDA Euro Question Bank (EQB)¹⁴, UK Data Archive¹⁵, CLOSER¹⁶, Schema.org¹⁷, and others). The goal is to identify consistent and interoperable metadata fields that can be used to register different entity types, referencing existing controlled vocabularies or adapting them where needed.

The section compiles metadata field alternatives from widely recognized sources to describe six main entity types:

- Variable
- Question
- Audiovisual segment
- Image area
- Sound segment
- Textual segment

As the next step, the report moves from defining general principles of controlled vocabularies to examining specific entity types requiring precise metadata descriptions. We begin with variables, as they represent the central unit of analysis in quantitative data and serve as a bridge between raw data, instruments, and interpretative outputs.

4.1 Entity type: Variables

Metadata for variables is central to ensuring that datasets are machine-actionable and human-readable across archives, repositories, and PID infrastructures. Although different organizations and tools vary in detail, most converge on two core elements: *variable name* and *variable label*.

¹² <https://www.gesis.org/en/research/research-area-research-data-management/archiving-practices>

¹³ <https://ddialliance.org/ddi-profiles>

¹⁴ <https://eqb.CESSDA.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://beta.ukdataservice.ac.uk/datacatalogue/studies/>

¹⁶ <https://ucldata.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/CLOS/overview?homepageld=37322760>

¹⁷ <https://schema.org/docs/schemas.html>

4.1.1 GESIS: Variable Metadata

At GESIS, the DDI-Codebook (DDI-C)¹⁸ standard is currently used as a metadata format for documenting and archiving products, projects, and processes. DDI elements, which support the version DDI-Lifecycle (DDI-L), are necessary to cover the entire life cycle of research data and ensure the interchangeability and reusability of metadata externally and internally in the archive. The DDILimDAS (DDI-Lifecycle application¹⁹) [8] aims to develop a metadata schema in the DDI-L format and convert the products, projects, and processes to DDI-L. In this process, the metadata schemes of several repositories/services were evaluated for similarities and differences, including:

- GESIS Search
- CBE (Codebook Explorer)
- CharmStats (Software to harmonize and recode variables)
- DSDM (Dataset Documentation Manager)
- da|ra (Registration Agency for Social and Economic Data)
- datorium (Repository for social science and economic science data)
- Missy (Microdata Information System is an online service platform that provides structured metadata for official statistics)
- Stardat (Data Archiving Suite)

Across these systems, GESIS consistently retains two fields: variable name and variable label:

- Variable name
- Variable label

¹⁸ <https://ddialliance.org/ddi-codebook>

¹⁹ <https://search.gesis.org/>

Information on Dataset: Variables			
4.17	Variable		Container element ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/l:VariableScheme/l:Variable/l:VariableName/r:String + ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/l:LogicalProduct/l:VariableScheme/r:VariableReference/r:TypeOfObject="Variable" + ddi:DDIInstance/g:Group/g:Subgroup/s:StudyUnit/l:LogicalProductReference/r:TypeOfObject="LogicalProduct"
4.17.1	Variable Name	Identifier of variable within a dataset; Name of variable; Name of target variable; Identifier of variable within a dataset	
4.17.2	Alt. Name	Alternative name for target variable	ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/l:VariableScheme/l:Variable/l:VariableName (with @isPreferred="true") + /r:String + ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/l:LogicalProduct/l:VariableScheme/r:VariableReference/r:TypeOfObject="Variable" + ddi:DDIInstance/g:Group/g:Subgroup/s:StudyUnit/l:LogicalProductReference/r:TypeOfObject="LogicalProduct"
4.17.3	Variable Label	Label of variable for display; Variable identifier	ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/l:VariableScheme/l:Variable/r:Label/r:Content + ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/l:LogicalProduct/l:VariableScheme/r:VariableReference/r:TypeOfObject="Variable" + ddi:DDIInstance/g:Group/g:Subgroup/s:StudyUnit/l:LogicalProductReference/r:TypeOfObject="LogicalProduct"
4.17.4	Alt. Label	Alternative for target variable	ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/l:VariableScheme/l:Variable/r:Label/r:TypeOfLabel (with @codeListName="GesisTypeOfLabel"="ispreferred/isnotpreferred") + ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/l:LogicalProduct/l:VariableScheme/r:VariableReference/r:TypeOfObject="Variable" + ddi:DDIInstance/g:Group/g:Subgroup/s:StudyUnit/l:LogicalProductReference/r:TypeOfObject="LogicalProduct"

Figure 3: GESIS: Core Fields for Variable Description

These serve as baseline metadata for variable registration, ensuring compatibility with external PID systems and controlled vocabularies.

Building on the GESIS practice, the next perspective comes from the DDI Alliance itself. As the origin of the DDI standards, the Alliance sets out a minimal but broadly accepted model for variable metadata.

4.1.2 DDI Alliance: Core Variable Metadata

The DDI Alliance defines a minimal but essential set of metadata fields for variables, focusing on:

- Variable name: the technical or short name used in datasets.
- Variable label: a descriptive title or phrase summarizing the variable's content.

Variable

Describes the structure of a Variable. This is the applied expression of a data item within a data set and maps to the GSIM ImplementedVariable. In addition to the standard name, label, and description, includes a reference to a source parameter, represented variable, conceptual variable, universe, concept, question, source variable, and embargo information. It identifies the normal source of the data in the variable, the unit of analysis, whether the variable provides temporal or geographic information, or serves as a weight for other variables in the data, and provides a full description of its representation.

Properties

Name	Type		Description
VariableName	NameType	0..n	A name for the Variable. May be expressed in
Label	LabelType	0..n	A display label for the Variable. Supports mul
Description	StructuredStringType	0..1	A description of the content and purpose of
OutParameter	ParameterType	0..1	Assigns a parameter that contains output fro
SourceParameterReference	ParameterType	0..1	Reference to an OutParameter that serves as
SourceVariableReference	Variable	0..n	Reference to variable(s) used as a basis for re

Figure 4: DDI Alliance: Core Fields for Variable Description²⁰

While the DDI Alliance outlines the essential elements required to describe a variable, other institutions have opted for more detailed approaches. The UK Data Archive, for example, extends documentation beyond names and labels, including contextual information such as survey questions and response categories.

4.1.3 UK Data Archive — Extended Variable Metadata

As a reference point, the UK Data Archive uses a richer metadata set when documenting variables. In addition to the variable name and label, it includes:

- Variable: the technical name of the variable.
- Label: a human-readable description of the variable’s meaning.
- Question text: the exact wording of the survey or questionnaire item that generated the variable.
- Responses: the list or description of valid answer options or values.

²⁰ <https://docs.ddialliance.org/DDI-Lifecycle/3.3/model/item-types/Variable/#variable>

Discover > Variables > Variable

Variable My Variables

UK Data Service variable record for:

New Russia Barometer XVIII, 2009

[<< Previous variable](#) | [Add to My Variables](#) | [Next variable >>](#)
[View response percentages](#) | [View survey catalogue record](#)

VARIABLE DETAILS

Variable	D7	
Label	D7. How long do you think it will be before Russia becomes a normal society?	
Question text	If not definitely normal, how long do you think it will be before Russia becomes a normal society?	
Responses	1 1-2 years	32
	2 3-5 years	155
	3 6-10 years	323
	4 Never	124
	5 Difficult to know if it ever will be normal	326
	9 Don't know	290
Disclaimer	Please note that these frequencies are not weighted.	
Location	New Russia Barometer XVIII, 2009	

Figure 5: UK Data Archive — Extended Variable Metadata Including Question and Response Details²¹

The comparison of GESIS, DDI Alliance, and the UK Data Archive shows a shared consensus around two essential elements, i.e., variable name and label. Recognizing that variables form the operational backbone of quantitative data and must be consistently registered is what unites them. Building on this, the following section turns to survey questions, which provide the source context from which variables are derived.

While variables capture the operationalized data, their origins are often found in survey or questionnaire items. Documenting questions preserves the original wording, purpose, and response structure, ensuring comparability across surveys and languages. The following subsections review approaches from GESIS, CESSDA, the DDI Alliance, CLOSER, and Schema.org, highlighting minimal model structures that include identifiers, labels, texts, and response domains.

²¹ https://discover.ukdataservice.ac.uk/variables/variable/?id=6444_V156

4.2 Entity type: Questions

Survey questions link conceptual frameworks with collected data, forming the foundation of social science research. They capture the original wording, intent, and response structure of the data collection instrument. For this reason, standardized question metadata is critical for ensuring comparability and reusability across studies and languages.

This section reviews how different schemas document questions as distinct entities. GESIS applies a concise model with identifiers and labels for clarity and reference. CESSDA's EuroQuestion-Bank (EQB) provides a structured, multilingual approach designed for cross-national interoperability. Finally, the DDI Alliance extends the model by including explicit response domains. These approaches illustrate the core and extended elements needed for effective question-level metadata.

4.2.1 GESIS — Core Question Metadata

GESIS uses a concise metadata set for describing survey questions [9]:

- Question-ID — a unique identifier for the question.
- Question Label — a short descriptive title.
- Question Title — a more formal or full title of the question.

Element No. of the metadata schema	Element	Definition and remarks	DDI 3.2 Mapping recommendation
Information on Questions Et Answers: Questions			
6	Questions	Questions of the study	Container element
6.1	Question-ID	ID of the question	ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/dc:QuestionScheme/dc:QuestionItem/r:UserID (with @typeOfUserID="QuestionID")
6.2	Reference of the question	Reference of questions on various elements	Container element
6.2.1	Relation to Survey Instrument	Association of question with an instrument	ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/dc:ControlConstructScheme/dc:QuestionConstruct/dc:QuestionReference/r:TypeOfObject="QuestionItem" + ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/dc:ControlConstructScheme/dc:Sequence/dc:ControlConstructReference/r:TypeOfObject="QuestionConstruct"
6.2.2	Relation to Answers	Reference to code list within the question	ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/dc:QuestionScheme/dc:QuestionItem/d:CodeDomain/r:CodeListReference/r:TypeOfObject="CodeList" + ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/dc:QuestionScheme/dc:QuestionGrid/dc:GridDimension/d:CodeDomain/r:CodeListReference/r:TypeOfObject="CodeList"
6.2.3	Relation to Concepts/Categories	Reference to concept within the question	ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/dc:QuestionScheme/dc:QuestionItem/r:ConceptReference/r:TypeOfObject="Concept" + ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/dc:QuestionScheme/dc:QuestionGrid/r:ConceptReference/r:TypeOfObject="Concept"
6.3	Question Label	Label of question for display	Container element
6.3.1	Question Title	Label of question for display; Question title	ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/dc:QuestionScheme/dc:QuestionItem/dc:QuestionItemName (with @context="title") + /r:String
6.3.2	Question Number	Question Number	ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/dc:QuestionScheme/dc:QuestionItem/dc:QuestionItemName (with @context="questionNumber") + /r:String
6.4	Specific Question		Container element
6.4.1	Specific Differentiation	"No specific distinction"; "Standard-specificity"	ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/dc:QuestionScheme/dc:QuestionItem/dc:QuestionItemName (with @context="SpecificName") + /r:String + for any further specification ddi:DDIInstance/g:ResourcePackage/dc:QuestionScheme/dc:QuestionItem/r:BasedOnObject/r:BasedOnReference/r:TypeOfObject="QuestionItem" (ID of the first)
6.4.2	Specific Question	specific question	Container element

Figure 6: GESIS: Core Metadata Fields for Survey Questions

The GESIS model prioritizes simplicity and clarity, and other initiatives expand the scope of question metadata. CESSDA, for instance, has developed a multilingual structure to ensure that questions can be compared and reused across countries.

4.2.2 CESSDA: Structured *QuestionItem* Metadata

The CESSDA EuroQuestion-Bank (EQB) provides cross-national access to survey questions in multiple languages. Its metadata schema centers on the *QuestionItem*, which includes:

- *QuestionItem-ID* — unique identifier for the question item.
- *QuestionItemName* — short or technical name.
- *QuestionItemText* — the full text of the question.

The CESSDA EuroQuestion-Bank (EQB) [10] project implements a cross-national question bank with a central search facility across all CESSDA’s survey holdings to display survey questions in different languages in a user-friendly way.

Table 1: EQB metadata schema

No.	Property	Occ	Lang	Type	Definition	Remark
Information on question(s)						
1	question	1-n	n.a.	n.a.	A question in EQB can be a single question item or a question grid.	
1.1*7	questionItem	0-n	n.a.	n.a.	A question item is a single question that contains a version, an ID, a name, a text, a statement, an interviewer instruction and a number.	
1.1.1	questionItemVersion	0-1	no	xs:integer	A version number of the question item.	do not publish all versions, only the latest
1.1.2	questionItemID	1-n	no	xs:integer	An identifier for a question item the metadata refers to.	
1.1.3	questionItemName	0-n	yes	xs:string	A label of a question item the metadata refers to.	
1.1.4	questionItemText	1-n	yes	xs:string	A literal question item text.	
1.1.5	questionItemStatement	0-n	yes	xs:string	A prequestion and/or postquestion and other statements as part of the question item text.	

Figure 7: CESSDA: *QuestionItem* Structure for Multilingual Survey Metadata

The CESSDA approach demonstrates the value of cross-national comparability. The DDI Alliance builds on encoding response options alongside questions by explicitly including the response domain in the metadata schema.

4.2.3 DDI Alliance — Question Metadata with Response Domain

The DDI Alliance metadata schema describes questions using the `QuestionItem` type, adding an explicit response domain:

- `QuestionItemName` — identifier or short name.
- `QuestionText` — the exact wording of the question.
- `ResponseDomain` — the set of valid response options or range definitions.

Properties		
Name	Type	
<code>QuestionItemName</code>	<code>NameType</code>	0..n
<code>InParameter</code>	<code>InParameterType</code>	0..n
<code>OutParameter</code>	<code>ParameterType</code>	0..n
<code>Binding</code>	<code>BindingType</code>	0..n
<code>QuestionText</code>	<code>DynamicTextType</code>	0..n
<code>QuestionIntent</code>	<code>StructuredStringType</code>	0..1
<code>ResponseDomain</code>	<code>RepresentationType</code>	0..1
<code>ResponseDomainReference_ManagedMissingValuesRepresentation</code>	<code>ManagedMissingValuesRepresentation</code>	0..1
<code>ResponseDomainReference_ManagedScaleRepresentation</code>	<code>ManagedScaleRepresentation</code>	0..1
<code>ResponseDomainReference_ManagedNumericRepresentation</code>	<code>ManagedNumericRepresentation</code>	0..1
<code>ResponseDomainReference_ManagedDateTimeRepresentation</code>	<code>ManagedDateTimeRepresentation</code>	0..1
<code>ResponseDomainReference_ManagedTextRepresentation</code>	<code>ManagedTextRepresentation</code>	0..1

Figure 8: DDI Alliance : *QuestionItem* Fields Including Response Domain ²²

The DDI Alliance enriches the documentation of questions by linking them directly to their valid responses, but some projects emphasize more streamlined requirements. CLOSER, for example, applies a minimal structure tailored to the needs of longitudinal studies

4.2.4 CLOSER — Minimum Metadata Requirements for Questions

The Cohort & Longitudinal Studies Enhancement Resources (CLOSER) follows a minimal but functional approach for describing questions, similar to DDI but without the item name:

²² <https://ddialliance.github.io/ddimodel-web/DDI-L-3.2/item-types/QuestionItem/#questionitem>

- QuestionLabel — concise descriptor.
- QuestionText — the full wording of the question.
- ResponseDomain — definition of valid responses.

Questionnaires

Item	Description	Mandatory	DDI Mapping	DDI Documentation
Question Label	CAI name or label of the question	Yes	UserAttributePair	
Question Text	Text of question	Yes	QuestionText	https://ddialliance.github.io/ddimodel-web/DDI-L-3.2/item-types/QuestionItem/ or https://ddialliance.github.io/ddimodel-web/DDI-L-3.2/item-types/QuestionGrid/
Response Domain	How the respondent can answer the question e.g. code List, numeric, text etc.	Yes	RepresentationType	https://ddialliance.github.io/ddimodel-web/DDI-L-3.2/composite-types/RepresentationType/

Figure 9: CLOSER: Streamlined Question Metadata with Response Domain²³

Although CLOSER's streamlined model offers practical efficiency, it remains limited in interoperability beyond its immediate context. Schema.org, on the other hand, provides a more general framework for questions, but one that is not optimized for survey research.

²³ <https://ucldata.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/CLOS/pages/37323119/Minimum+Metadata+Requirements>

4.2.5 Schema.org: Question Entity

Schema.org defines a generic Question type; however, it is not tailored to survey-specific metadata needs and does not directly support elements such as question identifiers or multilingual text.

Question
A Schema.org Type
Thing > CreativeWork > Comment > Question

A specific question - e.g. from a user seeking answers online, or collected in a Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) document. [\[more...\]](#)

Property	Expected Type	Description
Properties from Question		
<code>acceptedAnswer</code>	Answer or ItemList	The answer(s) that has been accepted as best, typically on a Question/Answer site. Sites vary in their selection mechanisms, e.g. drawing on community opinion and/or the view of the Question author.
<code>answerCount</code>	Integer	The number of answers this question has received.
<code>eduQuestionType</code>	Text	For questions that are part of learning resources (e.g. Quiz), <code>eduQuestionType</code> indicates the format of question being given. Example: "Multiple choice", "Open ended", "Flashcard".
<code>parentItem</code>	Comment or CreativeWork	The parent of a question, answer or item in general. Typically used for Q/A discussion threads e.g. a chain of comments with the first comment being an Article or other CreativeWork. See also <code>comment</code> which points from something to a comment about it.
<code>suggestedAnswer</code>	Answer or ItemList	An answer (possibly one of several, possibly incorrect) to a Question, e.g. on a Question/Answer site.
Properties from Comment		
<code>downvoteCount</code>	Integer	The number of downvotes this question, answer or comment has received from the community.
<code>parentItem</code>	Comment or CreativeWork	The parent of a question, answer or item in general. Typically used for Q/A discussion threads e.g. a chain of comments with the first comment being an Article or other CreativeWork. See also <code>comment</code> which points from something to a

Figure 10: Schema.org: generic question entity not optimized for survey metadata²⁴

Across the reviewed standards, there is broad agreement on the importance of recording the exact wording of survey questions and their response domains. GESIS favors a concise model, CESSDA and DDI offer more structured formats with multilingual and response options, while CLOSER emphasizes minimum requirements for longitudinal studies. Table 5 Summarizes the models used as benchmarking.

²⁴ <https://schema.org/Question>

Entity type	Standard / Source	Core Metadata Fields from standards
Variables	GESIS (DDI-C/DDI-L)	Variable name, Variable label
	DDI Alliance	Variable name, Variable label
	UK Data Archive	Variable (technical name), Label
Questions	GESIS	Question-ID, Question Label, Question Title
	CESSDA EuroQuestion-Bank	QuestionItem-ID, QuestionItemName, QuestionItemText
	DDI Alliance	QuestionItemName, QuestionText
	CLOSER	QuestionLabel, QuestionText
	Schema.org	Generic Question (limited support)

Table 5: Core Fields for Variables and Questions

Together, these models emphasize the shared approach to capturing question text and labels, and the divergence in how identifiers and response domains are handled. This diversity underscores the need for a harmonized schema that balances minimal interoperability with sufficient richness for reuse toward PID-enabled registration of questions as citable research entities.

In addition to variables and questions, the Social Sciences research increasingly relies on qualitative data such as text excerpts, sound, video, and images. These require finer-grained description at the segment level to make them discoverable, citable, and linkable via persistent identifiers. Although widely used in web contexts, Schema.org lacks survey elements and provides metadata for audio and video segments. The following section shifts the focus beyond structured instruments to unstructured qualitative materials such as text, audio, video, and image segments. It addresses the metadata requirements for segments across different media types.

4.3 Entity type: Textual, Audio/Video Segments and Images

Beyond variables and questions, research datasets increasingly include qualitative data that require equally standardized documentation. These may be textual excerpts, audio recordings, video segments, or spatial regions within images. Ensuring such fragments are consistently described, identified, and linkable through persistent identifiers is essential for enabling reuse and precise citation.

This section reviews how different metadata standards approach the description of segments across text, audio, video, and images. It begins with the DDI Alliance model, which provides composite types to describe fragments with fine temporal or spatial precision. It then considers Schema.org, which offers a simplified but widely adopted structure relevant in web contexts and for interoperability with linked data environments. The examples and figures presented here illustrate how segment-level metadata supports the goals of discoverability, machine-actionability, and FAIR-compliant integration across diverse audio and video data.

4.3.1 DDI Alliance

The DDI Alliance metadata schema supports fine-grained description of content fragments across various media types. It does so through specialized segment types that capture temporal, textual, or spatial information.

- TextualType allows for precise referencing of character-based or line-based excerpts using LineParameter and CharacterParameter²⁵.
- SegmentType comprises Audio and Video Types. AudioType enables marking the start and end of an audio clip with AudioClipBegin and AudioClipEnd. Video Type descriptions use VideoClipBegin and VideoClipEnd to define temporal ranges²⁶.
- ImageAreaType defines spatial regions in images using Shape and Coordinates²⁷.

This model is particularly suited to archives or repositories that handle interview transcripts, audiovisual footage, or annotated images, enabling these elements to be cited and retrieved independently. Figures 11–15 illustrate how each segment type is represented within the DDI-Lifecycle metadata model.

²⁵ <https://ddialliance.github.io/ddimodel-web/DDI-L-3.2/composite-types/TextualType/?highlight=textualtype>

²⁶ <https://ddialliance.github.io/ddimodel-web/DDI-L-3.2/composite-types/VideoType/>

²⁷ <https://ddialliance.github.io/ddimodel-web/DDI-L-3.2/composite-types/ImageAreaType/>

SegmentType

A structure used to express explicit segments or regions within different types of external materials (Textual, **Audio**, Video, XML, and Image). Provides the appropriate start, stop, or region definitions for each type.

Properties

Name	Type		Description
Textual	TextualType	0..n	Defines the segment of textual content used by the parent object. Can identify
Audio	AudioType	0..n	Describes the type and length of the audio segment.
Video	VideoType	0..n	Describes the type and length of the video segment.
XML	string	0..n	An X-Pointer expression identifying a node in the XML document.
ImageArea	ImageAreaType	0..n	Defines the shape and area of an image used as part of a location representa

Figure 11: DDI-Lifecycle Composite Types for Segments (SegmentType)

TextualType

Defines the segment of textual content used by the parent object. Can identify a set of lines and or characters used to define the segment.

Properties

Name	Type		Description
LineParameter	LineParameterType	0..1	Specification of the line and offset for the beginning and e
CharacterParameter	CharacterParameterType	0..1	Specification of the character offset for the beginning and

Figure 12: DDI-Lifecycle Composite Types for Segments (Text)

AudioType

Describes the type and length of the audio segment.

Properties

Name	Type		Description
TypeOfAudioClip	CodeValueType	0..1	The type of audio clip provided. Supports the use of a controlled vocab
AudioClipBegin	string	0..1	The point to begin the audio clip. If no point is provided the assumptio
AudioClipEnd	string	0..1	The point to end the audio clip. If no point is provided the assumption

Figure 13: DDI-Lifecycle Composite Types for Segments (AudioType)

Video Type

Describes the type and length of the **video** segment.

Properties

Name	Type		Description
TypeOf Video Clip	CodeValueType	0..1	The type of video clip provided. Supports the use of a controlled vc
Video ClipBegin	string	0..1	The point to begin the video clip. If no point is provided the assum
Video ClipEnd	string	0..1	The point to end the video clip. If no point is provided the assumpt

Figure 14: DDI-Lifecycle Composite Types for Segments (VideoType)

Image AreaType

Defines the shape and area of an **image** used as part of a location representation. The shape is defined as a Rectangle, Circle, or Polygon and Coordinates provides the information required to define it.

Properties

Name	Type		Description
Shape	string	0..1	A fixed set of valid responses includes Rectangle, Circle, and Polygon.
Coordinates	string	0..1	A comma-delimited list of x,y coordinates, listed as a set of adjacent points for rectan;

Figure 15: DDI-Lifecycle Composite Types for Segments (Image areaType)

While the DDI model provides a highly structured and detailed approach, technical complexity may limit its adoption. Schema.org offers an alternative model focusing on simplicity and interoperability for broader web integration and lightweight implementation.

4.3.2 Schema.org

Schema.org provides a simplified but widely adopted structure for describing media segments, especially in web-based contexts. For video segments, Schema.org uses StartOffset and EndOffset to define the temporal boundaries of a clip. This model benefits interoperability with platforms and services relying on JSON-LD or RDF for structured data markup.

For example, the PANGAEA (Qualidataservice) dataset repository uses Schema.org terms to improve the discoverability and interlinking of video excerpts within scientific datasets.

#	Name	Short Name	Unit	Principal Investigator	Method/Device	Comment
1	Data ID	Data ID				
2	File name	File name				
3	General data format	Data format				
4	File format	File format				
5	File size	File size	kByte			kBytes
6	Event duration	Event duration				video duration
7	Device type	Device				
8	Data collection date	DC date				
9	Data collection location	DC location				
10	File content	Content				video title
11	Keywords	Keywords				beekeeping; honey hunting
12	Start offset	startOffset				video segments
13	End offset	endOffset				video segments
14	File content	Content				title segments
15	Annotation	Annotation				biologist
16	Annotation	Annotation				anthropologist
17	Keywords	Keywords				keywords segments

Figure 16: PANGAEA (Qualidataservice) Using Schema.org Terms for Video Segment Discoverability and Linking

Figure 17 and Figure 18 show the application of Schema.org properties to audiovisual segments.

Figure 17: Schema.org Properties for Video Segments (StartOffset) ²⁸

²⁸ Schema.org VideoObject specification: <https://schema.org/VideoObject>

Figure 18: Schema.org Properties for Video Segments (EndOffset) ²⁹

Reviewing metadata schema for variables, questions, and qualitative data segments highlights the need for a harmonized approach that can operate consistently across different data types. To achieve true interoperability, these descriptive elements must be integrated into a standard schema that captures their internal structure and connects them through persistent identifiers (PIDs). This ensures that a variable, a survey question, or a short video excerpt can all be referenced, discovered, and cited with the same precision as a dataset or publication.

To ensure true interoperability and machine-actionability, these descriptive elements must be integrated into a shared metadata schema that captures their internal structure and enables their registration through Persistent Identifiers (PIDs).

The following section outlines this proposed metadata schema for the PID registration service, drawing on the stable fields and best practices identified in the previous sections. This schema serves as the operational link between the existing metadata schema and the technical implementation of a PID registration service for dataset elements.

Section 4 highlighted how different standards—such as GESIS, DDI Alliance, CESSDA, UK Data Archive, CLOSER, and Schema.org—address variables, questions, and qualitative segments. While these approaches provide valuable models, they differ in scope, granularity, and interoperability, leaving gaps for consistent PID registration at the fragment level. The following section introduces an extended metadata schema based on this comparative review. This schema consolidates the most stable and widely accepted metadata elements identified in Section 4.

²⁹ Schema.org VideoObject specification: <https://schema.org/VideoObject>

5. Extended metadata schema for new entities

Building on the review of existing standards in Section 4, this section introduces an extended metadata schema specifically designed to support PID of dataset elements. These dataset elements include variables, survey questions, and non-tabular segments.

The proposed schema originates from the core fields identified across major initiatives (e.g., GESIS, DDI Alliance, UK Data Archive, CESSDA, CLOSER, Schema.org). It adapts them into a coherent structure suitable for machine-actionable PID registration. Harmonizing metadata fields across entity types enables precise referencing of dataset elements.

This schema ensures datasets are registered and assigned a PID, enabling their elements' registration and granular citation. As such, it fills a critical gap in current PID practices and supports new use cases in data discovery and research reproducibility.

The minimal required fields for registering new entity types follow the original schema's logic and are adapted for qualitative and segment-based content.

Entity	Field	Type / Format	Example / Value Reference Example ³⁰
Variable	Code / ID / Name	Plain-text	V280
	Label	Plain-text	LIFE PARTNER: VOCATIONAL SCHOOL DEGREE
Variable – Repetitive Across Datasets	DataFile Name	Physical instance. Name the file containing the variable in different dataset versions (same DOI).	ZA3000_v2-0-0.sav (SPSS Dataset) ZA3000_v2-0-0.por (SPSS Portable Dataset) ZA3000_Variablenliste.txt (Variable List) ZA3000_missing_v2-0-0.sps (Missing Values Definition) ZA3000_v2-0-0.dta.zip (Stata Dataset) Example: GESIS Variable V280 Example: https://search.gesis.org/variables/exploredata-ZA3000_VarV280
	DataFile Format	File format for the dataset version.	ZA****.dta (Stata) ZA****.por (SPSS Portable*) ZA****.sav (SPSS*) CSV Excel Txt *SPSS is the authoritative format at GESIS
	Alternative Identifier	Specific sheet or tab name in Excel files.	Variable's worksheet name

³⁰ https://search.gesis.org/variables/exploredata-ZA3000_VarV280

Question and Answer	Question Number / Code / ID / Name	Plain-text	S33
	Question Item Name / Title	Plain-text	S33G – Vocational school qualification
	Question Text	Plain-text	<p>What professional training qualification does your partner have? Which of this list applies? Please tell me the corresponding code letters.</p> <p></p> <p>https://search.gesis.org/variables/exploredata-ZA3000_VarV280</p>
	Response Domain	Definition of the type of possible responses (textual, numeric, categorical, etc.).	—

Table 6: Extended metadata schema to register variables and questions.

ID	FIELD NAME	DESCRIPTION	PID SERVICE LEVEL	NOTES / CONTROLLED VOCABULARY
1	Study (or Dataset) DOI*	DOI or PID identifying the study where the entity appears	Required for any PID	Identifier_Type required
2	Entity Name	Code/ID of the entity (e.g., question code, segment ID)	Required	Plain-text
3	Entity Label	Human-readable label or title	Required	Plain-text
4	PID Proposal*	Suggested PID; auto-assigned if not provided	Required	<prefix>/<suffix>
5	Landing Page*	URL to detailed entity description	Required	URL
6	Resource Type*	Controlled term for entity type	Required	Controlled list (Variable, Question/Answer, Sound segment, Audiovisual segment, Text excerpt, Image area)
7	Title	Generated or supplied title	Required	Include entity name + label
8	Creators	Main researchers/authors	Required	Personal or institutional
9	Publisher	Responsible entity	Required	Institutional
10	Publication Date	YYYY-MM-DD	Required	Date of publication
11	Availability	Access conditions	Required	Controlled list (Delivery, OnSite, etc.)
12	Description / Abstract	Additional info	Required	Plain-text
13	RelatedItem	Related resource	Optional	Controlled list (ResourceType, e.g., Variable linked to Question)
13.1	RelatedIdentifier	PID of related resource	Optional	<prefix>/<suffix>
13.1.1	RelatedIdentifier_Type	PID system name	Optional	PID System - e.g., DOI, Handle

13.1.2	Relation_Type	Description of the relationship	If RelatedIdentifier is used, Mandatory (M)	Controlled list (IsContinuedBy, Continues, Describes, HasVersion, IsVersionOf, IsNewVersionOf, IsPreviousVersionOf, IsDocumentedBy, IsCompiledBy, IsVariantFormOf, IsDerivedFrom, IsSourceOf, IsRequiredBy, IsObsoletedBy) Controlled list variables relations [11].
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Table 7: Extended metadata schema to register variables and qualitative data.

The section is structured as follows:

- Section 5.1 presents the core elements of the proposed schema, grouped by entity type (variables, questions, segments).
- Section 5.2 outlines the alignment of each element with PID metadata requirements, including interoperability with existing PID services and metadata registries.
- Section 5.3 provides illustrative examples of how the schema can be applied in real-world PID registration scenarios.

5.1 Extended metadata schema for fragments

This section presents a comprehensive overview of metadata variations for fragments (segments) across the main entity types: Audiovisual segment, Image area, Sound segment, and Text excerpt. Each includes required metadata, segment-specific fields, and explanations of their use in each context.

Annotate attributes are needed for each entity to pinpoint specific segments or fragments within digital resources, including text, images, audio, and video segments. For example, it could be a paragraph in a text document, an area of an image, a segment of an audio file, a segment of a video, or a region of a frame.

5.1.1 Audiovisual Segments

Reference a video clip or a scene within a longer audiovisual file (e.g., interaction moment, non-verbal gesture, important response).

- **Key fields:**

Field	Type	Example	Explanation
resourceType	string	"Audiovisual"	Standardized format indicating the media type.
isFragment	boolean	TRUE	Indicates a portion of an AV file.
entityCode	string	"VIDseg_01"	Unique code or identifier for the segment.
entityLabel	string	"Doctor introduces medication"	Descriptive tag for the segment.
title	string	"VIDseg_01_Doctor introduces medication"	Auto-generated or customized title (entityCode + entityLabel).
startOffset	string	"00:01:32.000"	Start of the fragment (hh:mm:ss.mmm).
endOffset	string	"00:01:55.000"	End of the fragment (hh:mm:ss.mmm).

Table 8: Extended metadata schema to register qualitative data: Audiovisual Segments

Qualitative Data /non-numeric or non-coded data annotations for different data types			
Audio	Fragment selector of time [1] and space [2] dimensions	FragmentSelector [1] #t=00,00 or #t=00:00,00:00	[1] starting and ending point of an audio fragment, in minutes and seconds.
Video	Fragment selector of time [1] and space [2] dimensions	FragmentSelector [1] #t=00,00 or #t=00:00,00:00 [2] #xywh	[1] The starting and ending points of the video fragment are in minutes and seconds. #t=20,27" or #t=00:20,00:27 (between 20 and 27 seconds) https://av.tib.eu/media/12780#t=00:20,00:27

Table 9: Qualitative Data /non-numeric or non-coded data annotations for audio and video

5.1.2 Image Area

Identify a region or annotation within an image (e.g., selected area in a photo, a focus region in a scan).

- **Key fields:**

Field	Type	Example	Explanation
resourceType	string	"Image"	Media type.
isFragment	boolean	TRUE	Marks a sub-region of a larger image.
entityCode	string	"IMGseg_07"	Unique code or identifier for the image area.
entityLabel	string	"Facial expression region"	Describes what is marked in the image.

Field	Type	Example	Explanation
title	string	"IMGseg_07_Facial expression region"	Auto-generated or customized title (entityCode + entityLabel).
shape	string	"rectangle"	Shape of the selected area (e.g., rectangle, polygon, circle).
coordinates	object	{ "x": 100, "y": 150, "width": 200, "height": 100 }	Area of interest in pixel units or % if normalized.

Table 10: Extended metadata schema to register qualitative data: Image Area

Qualitative Data /non-numeric or non-coded data annotations for different data types			
Image	Fragment selector of the space [1] dimension	FragmentSelector [2] #xywh	Example for image area coordinates: xywh= pixel:763,2,183,206"
		<p>[1] A region or a fragment or an image might be represented as #xywh=50,50,180,180, which would specify a rectangular portion of an image starting at x (horizontal starting point), y (vertical starting point), w (width), and h (height) of the selection. Annotations need to be not only accurate but also interoperable across various platforms and devices.</p>	

Table 11: Qualitative Data /non-numeric or non-coded data annotations for images

5.1.3 Sound Segments

Capture specific utterances, pauses, or tones in an audio file (e.g., a question, an interruption, a vocal cue).

- **Key fields:**

Field	Type	Example	Explanation
resourceType	string	"Sound"	Identifies this as an audio resource.
isFragment	boolean	TRUE	Denotes a slice of a sound file.
entityCode	string	"SNDseg_05"	Unique code or identifier for the sound segment.
entityLabel	string	"Physician asks about symptoms"	Semantic meaning of the audio clip.
title	string	"SNDseg_05_Physician asks about symptoms"	Auto-generated or customized title (entityCode + entityLabel).
startOffset	string	"00:00:45.000"	Start timestamp (hh:mm:ss.mmm).
endOffset	string	"00:01:00.000"	End timestamp (hh:mm:ss.mmm).

Table 12: Extended metadata schema to register qualitative data: Sound Segments

Qualitative Data /non-numeric or non-coded data annotations for different data types			
Audio	Fragment selector of time [1] and space [2] dimensions	FragmentSelector [1] #t=00,00 or #t=00:00,00:00	[1] starting and ending point of an audio fragment, in minutes and seconds.

Table 13: Qualitative Data /non-numeric or non-coded data annotations for Audio

5.1.4 Text Excerpts

Highlight specific phrases, paragraphs, or tokens in longer text documents (e.g., interview excerpts, thematic codes).

- **Key fields:**

Field	Type	Example	Explanation
resourceType	string	"Text"	Indicates the media type.
isFragment	boolean	TRUE	Marks this as a fragment of a larger text.
entityCode	string	"TXTseg_02"	Unique code or identifier for the text segment.
entityLabel	string	"Excerpt from Paragraph 2"	Human-readable label for the segment.
title	string	"TXTseg_02_Excerpt from Paragraph 2"	Auto-generated or customized title (entityCode + entityLabel).
startOffset	string	"32"	Character position where the fragment starts.
endOffset	string	"312"	Character position where the fragment ends.

Table 14: Extended metadata schema to register qualitative data: Text Excerpts

Qualitative Data /non-numeric or non-coded data annotations for different data types			
Text	Character length [1] Start [2] and end [3] character position Start [4] and end line [5].	FragmentSelector ³¹ TextualBody / Plain Text	[1]410 [2] 49, [3] 100 [4] 23, [5] 27 " <u>char=49,410</u> "
<p>Quantitative data, Qualitative data[¶]</p> <p>For each entity we need to annotate properties in attributes to pinpointing specific segments or fragments within digital resources, not only non-numeric, non-coded datums, but also text, pictures, audio and video segments accordingly. <i>As examples, it could be a paragraph in a text document, an area of an image, a segment of an audio file, a segment of a video along with a region of a frame. A region or a fragment or an image might be represented as #xywh=50,50,180,180, which would specify a rectangular portion of an image starting where x (horizontal starting point), y (vertical starting point), w (width), and h (height) of the selection.</i> Annotations need to be not only accurate but also interoperable across various platforms and devices.¶</p>			

Table 15: Qualitative Data /non-numeric or non-coded data annotations for Text

To prevent collisions and confusion:

- Ensure unique combinations of entityCode + entityLabel
- Optionally append:
 - _seg1, _frag01, or timestamp-based suffixes
- Use hash values or UUIDs when automatic suffixing is not viable

Table 16 presents the main Entity Types that can be registered at the fragment level within a larger resource, specifying the technical fields required to identify them, the reference standards they follow, and the purpose of each. For video and audio, in addition to specialized standards such as W3C Media Fragments, ELAN, and MPEG-7, Schema.org also defines properties like *startOffset* and *endOffset* for *VideoObject* and *AudioObject*, widely used to describe temporal segments on the web.

Multiple standards are listed for each entity type because no specification universally covers all technical, semantic, and interoperability needs for identifying fragments. Some, like W3C Media Fragments³², provide a general URI-based model to point to time or spatial fragments;

³¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model/#range-selector>

³² <https://www.w3.org/TR/media-frags/>

others, like MPEG-7 (ISO/IEC 15938)³³, define rich descriptors for audiovisual content. In the case of images, the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF)³⁴ enables precise region referencing, while the Web Annotation³⁵ standard defines spatial shapes and coordinates. For text, the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI)³⁶ offers robust frameworks for marking up excerpts.

The listed standards complement each other: some focus on technical positioning (e.g., time offsets, coordinates), others on semantic annotation (e.g., describing the content of the fragment), and some on web discoverability (e.g., Schema.org). They provide the metadata necessary to locate, describe precisely, and interlink fragments for reproducible citation, machine-actionable linking, and compliance with FAIR principles.

Entity Type	Segment Fields	Standards / Origin	Purpose
Audiovisual	startTime, endTime	W3C Media Fragments, MPEG-7, Schema.org (VideoObject)	Identify and point to specific video segments within a larger file.
Image	coordinates	IIIF, W3C Media Fragments, Web Annotation	Identify and describe spatial regions or annotations within an image.
Sound	startTime, endTime	ISO/IEC 15938 (MPEG-7), Open Annotation, Schema.org (AudioObject)	Capture and describe sound excerpts within an audio recording.
Text	startCharOffset, endCharOffset	W3C Web Annotation, TEI,	Identify character-based excerpts within a larger text.

Table 16: Entity types, segmentation fields, and relevant standards for fragment identification

This report has outlined the rationale and structure for extending metadata schemas to cover dataset elements at a finer level of granularity, addressing both quantitative and qualitative data types. The proposed approach supports interoperability and reuse in line with FAIR principles by aligning controlled vocabularies and identifying stable fields across existing tools.

6. Conclusion

This report has demonstrated the extended metadata used to document aggregated resources, including dataset elements such as variables, questions, and qualitative segments. By reviewing standards and tools from GESIS, the DDI Alliance, CESSDA, the UK Data Archive, CLOSER, Schema.org, and others, we identified commonalities and gaps in how these entities are currently represented. Across all approaches, *variable names and labels* emerge as minimal

³³ <https://mpeg.chiariglione.org/standards/mpeg-7> (overview)

³⁴ <https://iiif.io/>

³⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model/>

³⁶ <https://tei-c.org/>

denominators, while questions and media segments require additional fields such as text, identifiers, and starting and ending points.

The proposed *Resource_Type* vocabulary (variable, question, text excerpt, sound segment, audiovisual segment, image area) addresses this gap. It ensures that dataset elements can be treated as first-class research entities, allowing for precise registration, citation, and discovery. This aligns with best practices on granularity and provides the foundation for interoperable PID registration.

From the perspective of the FAIR principles, the proposed schema contributes by:

- Findable: enabling lower granularity level PIDs for dataset elements, making variables, questions, and media segments individually retrievable.
- Accessible: ensuring these elements can be accessed consistently across repositories and platforms through standardized or mapped metadata.
- Interoperable: in line with existing models (DDI, COAR, Schema.org) while adopting controlled vocabularies that bridge quantitative and qualitative data.
- Reusable: preserving context through identifiers, labels, and segment intervals, which ensures that dataset elements can be reliably reused and cited in new research.

These specifications are already operationalized in the PID registration service [12] [13], with pilot implementations' vocabulary and metadata schema [14] [15] [16]. These tests included mappings to existing standards, validating the JSON file for bulk PID registration, and ensuring that repositories can register dataset elements at the required level of granularity. This prepares the project to advance the long-term goal of sustainable, FAIR-compliant research data. These contributions also directly support KonsortSWD's objectives within the NFDI framework by providing the technical foundation for more precise, reusable, and sustainable research data infrastructures.

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